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Session 2B

ZDC vs. Bitumen Aging: A Comparative Study of Aging Methods

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Aging

Aging Delay - Antioxidants

Antioxidant: ZDC

Antioxidants

Global antioxidant consortium

Zinc Diethyl-dithiocarbamate (ZDC) works well under standardized laboratory aging (thermal)

Publications:

Research Outline

Pressure Aging Vessel (PAV)

Aging States / Methods

Viennese Binder Aging (VBA)

Aging States / Methods

3xPAV

Thermal aging

VBA

Thermo-chemical aging

Light aged

Photo-thermal aging

Field aged

Light Aging

Aging States / Methods

3xPAV

Thermal aging

VBA

Thermo-chemical aging

Light aged

Photo-thermal aging

Field aged

Field Aging

Aging States / Methods

3xPAV

Thermal aging

VBA

Thermo-chemical aging

Light aged

Photo-thermal aging

Field aged

Research Outline

ATR-FTIR

Binder A

Binder A with ZDC

DSR – Master Curve

Key Findings

- **ZDC's power** as an antioxidant is **dependent on aging conditions & crude oil source!**
 - ZDC works best for **thermal standardized laboratory** aging with PAV
 - followed by **thermo-chemical aging (VBA)**
 - **Light and Field aging** showed the **least improvement**
- The **effectiveness of antioxidants** needs to be **tested under environmental aging conditions!**
 - However, **no laboratory method** could yet replicate **field conditions**